

Supplementary Material

1. Feedback links between core model variables

Source for all figures: https://github.com/Pendracus/MORDRED/blob/main/Diagrams_MORDRED.pdf.

Demography module

Suppl. Figure 1: Key variables and dynamics in the demographic module.

Labor module

Suppl. Figure 2: Key variables and dynamics in the labor module.

Energy module

Suppl. Figure 3: Key variables and dynamics in the energy module.

Land module

Suppl. Figure 4: Key variables and dynamics in the land module.

Economy module

Suppl. Figure 5: Key variables and dynamics in the economy module.

2. Comparison of qualitative scenario variables with model variables

Suppl. Table 1 contains a comparison between important variables from the selected scenarios and representation of those variables in MORDRED. The scenario variables are drawn from the translation protocols for the two scenarios which are mentioned in the main text. Although not all variables are reflected in the model's structure, we consider the representation sufficient to take the two storylines as basis for an 'early' and a 'late' transition scenario. Nevertheless, we wish to point out that it is important to keep in mind the missing variables when interpreting our simulation results.

Scenario variable (<i>FST5</i> / <i>BAU-GEG</i>)	Model representation
<i>Changes in the scale of economic activities</i>	Overall economic scale depends on sectoral output which changes endogenously in the model
<i>Changes in the size of human population</i>	Overall size of the human population depends on region- and age-specific death and birth rates which change endogenously in the model
<i>Economic scale in relation to well-being requirements</i>	No explicit well-being indicators; implicit through life expectancy and consumption of different basic goods (health, education etc.)
<i>Economic scale in relation to energy & material flows within the bioregion</i>	No representation
<i>Military & security</i>	Security expenses included in the public consumption of services
<i>Earth intensities</i>	Fossil fuel, energy, land, mineral, biomass and water intensity represented
<i>Duration of materials in economic sphere</i>	Representation through A-Matrix
<i>Changes in labor & capital intensity</i>	Increases or reductions possible
<i>Consumption inequality</i>	Increases or reductions possible

<i>Need-based allocation</i>	No representation
<i>Control over productive capacity</i>	No representation
Influence of unequal consumption on life expectancy	Mortality rates increase with decreases in per capita consumption
Influence of climate damages on life expectancy	Mortality rates are negatively affected by climate damages through reduced per capita consumption
Influence of violent conflicts on life expectancy	No representation
Evolution of per capita consumption	Consumption per capita disaggregated into 4 different classes and 3 world regions
Hegemonic discourse and values	No representation
Power distribution, monopoly of violence, political actors, conflict resolution	No representation
Trade regime	Global production system
Interregional inequality	Increases or reductions possible
Class inequality	Increases or reductions possible
Social policy	Increases or reductions in total government spending and spending in certain sectors
Military policy	Indirect representation through sectorial government spending for services and industry
Migration policy	Migration between formal and subsistence economy; no representation of other types of migration
Environmental policy	Reduction or increase of available fuels, protection of different land types (subsistence land, primary, secondary forests and agricultural land), changes in material inputs into the economic process, caused by recycling or product reuse
Economic policy	Representation of distribution, investment and technology.
Mode of production, goal and control of production	No representation of economic mode of production and socio-economic configurations
Allocation principles	Representation of territorial, class based, age based and egalitarian allocation
Productivity/intensity of economic production	Representation of labor productivity, capital productivity, land intensity, energy intensity, material intensity of production;
Energy types	Representation of carbon, petroleum and gas, fossil electricity, hydro-electricity, solar PV, wind electricity, nuclear electricity, biomass based energy
Mitigation	Mitigation through changes in economic structure
Adaptation	No explicit representation of adaptation. Adaptation capacity assumed to be a function of consumption per capita
Earth system	Representation of climate system, different land types, land conversion, energy, material, biomass and water extraction. Climate damages affecting output, land, labor and capital stocks, as well as land, labor and capital intensities. Pollution flows: air pollution, P&N pollution.

Suppl. Table 1: Comparison of scenario and model variables.